

From Resource Extraction to Algorithmic Governance: A Colonial Ecocritical Study of *Playground* by Richard Powers

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Abstract: *This paper discusses *Playground* (2024) by Richard Powers in terms of colonial extraction and neocolonial environmental exploitation by taking the sub-themes of artificial intelligence and plastic waste as the new modes of imperialism. The novel unveils the existence of colonial extraction logics within digital and technocratic regimes that claim to be neutral and efficient. The AI-based government becomes an alternative new form of colonial rule that governs the environment remotely, instead of ruling it directly as was done earlier. In conjunction with this, plastic is one of the storage sites of imperial histories of consumer capitalism and imperial circulation as an archival material. This production of garbage in the islands and the oceans reflects previous mining activities, converting the marginalized areas to sacrifice zones. *Playground* reveals the unequal distribution of environmental destruction and its historical construction through the connection of ecological destruction and neocolonial structures of power.*

Keywords: Colonialism, Neocolonialism, Ecocriticism, AI

Introduction

Ecocriticism is a relatively new concept that first appeared in the 1990s literary theory and cultural studies. William Rueckart originally used the word ecocriticism in his article *Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism* (1978) in order to focus

on the application of ecology and ecological principles to the study of literature. According to Cheryll Goltfelty (1996) ecocriticism is the study of the relationship between literature and the physical world. As a result, ecocritics evaluate artistic creations based on the relationship between humans and nature. Ecocriticism prominently focuses on raising awareness of environmental issues and responsibility among people because of the fact that environmental sustainability is crucial to human existence on Earth.

The dialogue between colonialism and environmentalism has been initiated by Rob Nixon in his essay *Environmentalism and Postcolonialism*, anthologised in the volume *Environmentalism and Postcolonialism* (2005). Nixon's confused interpretation of the terms "environmentalism" and "postcolonialism" is prompted by environmental activism and the opposition to colonial environmental exploitation in the former colonised African, Asian, and Latin American nations (Nixon 233). Postcolonial nations face marginalization in ecological practices, underrepresented in the global South. Despite colonialism's end, cultural and economic domination persists, with limitations and contradictions.

The term neo-colonialism was coined by the French philosopher Jean- Paul Sartre in 1956. It was first used by Kwame Nkrumah, a Ghanaian politician, in the context of African countries undergoing decolonization in the 1960s. Kwame Nkrumah views the transition to a 'neocolonial' situation as the last stage of imperialism, perpetuating colonialism through globalization and capitalism. This perpetuates economic inequalities and complicates the relationship between the economically privileged and the underprivileged, complicating postcolonial discourses. Neocolonialism is defined by Matthew G. Stanard in his 2018 book *European Overseas Empire, 1879-1999: A Short History* as the continuance or imposition of imperialist control by a state, often a former colonial power, over another state, typically a former colony that is ostensibly independent.

Neocolonialism is seen as a continuation of colonialism in postcolonial states relies on the expansion of capitalism. The ongoing crises in emerging and underdeveloped economies make the climate catastrophe more complicated from an intra-human perspective. The goal of the neocolonial system, which implies economic exploitation, is to promote a consumer culture by objectifying both human and nonhuman beings. Furthermore, the colonial powers' implementation of "extraction ecologies" is another way that the unequal human interaction is demonstrated (Miller 29).

Industrial Revolution, economically underdeveloped nations have been colonized by their natural resources, leading to resource-cursed society where the environment is subjected to poisonous gases and carbon concentration, hurting the ecosystem and ruining local population's livelihoods. (Nixon 30) Modern environmental theory has been characterized by the rise of so-called modernising ecologists, proposing increased and smaller-scale reforms within global capitalism to help avoid climate disaster without stopping economic growth, but socialist as well as deep ecologists believe that these tactics cannot work, because schemes like the paperless office, fuel economy have actually increased consumption and energy consumption instead of reducing its effects (Foster, Clark, and York 7-9).

Playground (2024), the fourteenth book by the well-known American author Richard Powers, is set in French Polynesia. The island of Makatea in French Polynesia, a historical location that was formerly colonised by France and exploited via heavy phosphate mining, a practice that destroyed its environment and epitomised the colonial extraction. *Playground* (2024), intertwines the lives of four characters Todd Keane, Rafi Young, Evelyne Beaulieu, and Ina Aroita. The novel examines the conflicts between human ambition and ecological fragility with a focus on the alluring promise and danger of technological innovation, the ocean's metaphysical depth as both environment and consciousness, and the lasting effects of colonial and neocolonial

dynamics in seascape transformation. *Playground* (2024) is a meditation on human connectedness and a warning allegory about dominion and care in an era of rapidly expanding technology and ecological disruption. Powers creates a novel that evokes both emotional resonance and intellectual inquiry through his careful prose and multi-layered storyline.

This research looks at neocolonialism and its impacts on ecosystem of Makatea, a French Polynesian island in the novel *Playground* (2024), and how these effects influence the lives of the locals. It also looks at how patterns of control and extraction from the physical world are carried over into the digital sphere by artificial intelligence, which is emerging as a modern instrument of consumerism and neocolonialism. Using this perspective, the study draws attention to how *Playground* (2024) intersects cultural displacement, ecological deterioration, and technological dominance.

Colonial Extraction of Resources

Playground (2024) by Richard Powers is a smooth, non-linear narrative and a story of personal tragedies, cultural myths, environmental issues, technology and colonial practices. The story centers around Makatea, a small French Polynesian island on which the phosphate deposits used to nourish the world, which is a historical way to describe the hideous colonial mining that scraped the island down to fertilizer to use on other lands. Powers inserts the childhood of Todd Keane in Chicago, a tech billionaire, and his friend-rival Rafi Young, a gifted programmer. The third one is Inna Aroita, a South Pacific-based sculptor. Alongside them, is Evelyne Beaulieu, an adventurous diver and an oceanographer. These four characters arrived Makatea to join a floating cities project. Power's oceanic tale combined and narrated as a braid that alters both the time, space and focalization. The movement of *Playground* in the early part of the century seems like a narrative of a coming-of-age story.

Powers makes a clear connection between Makatea's colonial past and the present, strengthening this neocolonial perspective. Initially, Richard Powers depicts the Makatea as a location where colonial extraction history reenacted under the pretence of progress and consumerism. In *Playground*, Makatea's past is clearly presented as an external colonial fate that was imposed long before the island's residents had any real control over their land or future. Makatea presented as a phosphate rich area and "the foreign joint venture came ashore in 1911 to take the magic rock. (Powers 31) which was an important colonial commodity because of its necessity in manufacturing of fertilizer which drove industrial agriculture in Europe and other imperial centres. As Frantz Fanon defines "colonies as source of raw material which, once turned into manufactured goods" (Powers 81) Environmental destruction is the most obvious example of colonial exploitation. Firstly Makatea is narrated as ecologically rich "reefs, soaring cliffs, and spectacular caves..." (Powers 31) however, the discovery of phosphate renders this biodiversity worthless. In order to mine the island heavily, forests were devastated, Indigenous people were uprooted, and exploited labour was brought in from all around Asia and the Pacific. Phosphate provided temporary wealth, yet Makatea gains infrastructure but also suffers. "miners succumbing to lung disease and children dying from contaminated water,"(Powers 31) revealing imperial prosperity's hidden price.

Closing of mines in 1966 illustrates the abandonment that follows colonisation. Makatea is abandoned when extraction is no longer profitable: "Makatea capsized when the phosphate mines closed."(Powers 32) The island as a boat metaphor highlights social and ecological breakdown, emphasising that colonization leaves behind irreversible harm rather than ending with departure. Colonialism was centred on the exploitation and manipulation of nature, which had long-lasting effects on people and cultural landscapes in addition to the environment. Huggan and Tiffin (2015) argues that postcolonial studies are beginning to recognize the close relationship between environmental problems and

European colonial aspirations for global supremacy and conquest. The racial and imperialist ideas that have supported colonial expansion are the root cause of these ecological worries. Because they were seen to be a part of nature, indigenous communities were frequently handled instrumentally, much like animals.

Neocolonial Power and Environmental Governance through AI

Playground rejects any story of emancipation or recovery, even when official colonial extraction finally comes to an end. Makatea enters a postcolonial state marked by economic reliance, ecological devastation and abandonment. The indication of an approaching catastrophe recalls the image of stories of ecological collapse seen in many postcolonial settings, as resource extraction results in environmental damage and cultural legacy loss. There is local government in name but not in practice. This situation is best shown by Didier Turi's position as mayor, where he has symbolic authority but no access to knowledge, experience or the ability to make decisions. Important agreements are signed without local permission and subsequently attributed to it, such as memoranda of understanding with foreign investors.

Neocolonialism appears in Playground through governance methods like as legal contracts, environmental evaluations, development rhetoric, and multinational alliances rather than armed occupation. Mayor Didier is shown in this novel, outlining a plan by Californian investors to transform Makatea into a floating city building project to attract tourists. The sleek advertising trail entices the islanders to dream of a better future by showcasing an ideal, environmentally friendly utopia that blends futuristic construction with the archaic Pacific way of life. "He began by reading a formal statement by the Californians that included commitments to the number and types of jobs that would be created, salary ranges for each category, and specs for the assembly facilities that would be built around the port"(Powers 268).

A new phase in the island's history of external dependency begins when the majority of residents support seasteading and the first opulent boat is launched into the ocean. As Powers said that "the humans had voted against themselves"(328). The proposed Makatea project by the American consortium is a prime example of how authority functions through documentation and delay, portraying resistance as untimely and choices as already taken. Importantly, the initiative is portrayed as development rather than an invasion. Colonialism achieved its desired aims through development projects. As Huggan and Tiffin (2015) critique "developmentality," an ideology that serves colonial interests and causes long-lasting environmental damage by justifying environmental degradation in the name of economic expansion. They argue that the colonial and neocolonial narrative of "development" is, at best, a kind of strategic altruism in which the self-described First World primarily uses financial and technical assistance to advance its own political and economic objectives (28).

AI in Playground is a consumerist instrument as well as a tool of narration. Richard Powers display the extension of the same colonialism and capitalism logics, into digital and ecological world, through technology and, specifically, artificial intelligence. Todd Keane enters his life history into Profunda, a computer memory archiver. This machine mediates his memories, choosing, organizing and thus telling them in the future. In this regard, AI is more like colonial archives: it keeps the narratives, but always in a filter that supports some voices instead of others. As according to Bender et al.(2021) dependence of AI on statistics is completely distorted by capitalism ethics and Eurocentric ideals.

AI Profunda and the Playground App offer to monitor global risk, optimize conservation tactics and model ecological futures. Despite being presented as ground-breaking instruments, these technologies work via abstraction and distance, turning intricate ecosystems into data sets. The process of remembering and human cultural memory is substituted with machine storage.

This is like the way colonizers used to dominate the writing and presentation of history in a neocolonial approach. A technological rationality on Makatea Island presents data about floating cities environmental and economic impacts through AI-generated information and chatbots. Although the dissemination of information seems democratic, the chatbot conversations reflect the investor's worldview, diminishing the islander's traditional ecological expertise rooted in cultural connections to their environment.

The Makatea seasteading project is presented as an endeavour where artificial intelligence has essentially taken over, highlighting the way in which technology automation has replaced human agency and action. As Manutahi Rao explained to Didier Turi "No human lifted a finger over this entire journey. The machine is doing everything. He just sits on deck, looking at the waves"(Powers 339). All aspects of the process, from planning to execution, are managed and depersonalized by AI systems, doing away with the human component that formerly characterized earlier forms of capitalism and colonial exploitation. Even the yacht captains, who were formerly considered to be emblems of wealth, status, and transnationalism, are now robots who have been trained to act as mechanical embodiments of global capitalism. The elimination of human empathy, accountability, and responsibility in colonial processes is shown by robots serving as boat captains. They implement preprogrammed orders, establishing a totalitarian, impersonal system of governance that embodies post-human colonisation.

Playground exposes neocolonialism as a modern ecological system rather than a remnant of the past through its portrayal of environmental governance. Instead of eliminating colonial hierarchies, technologies like AI Profunda and the Playground App digitalize and globalize them. By separating sustainability language from historical accountability, postcolonial ecocriticism enables us to observe how imperialism continues under the pretence of planetary care.

Plastic as Imperial Archive

Richard Powers presents a novel reassessment of colonial authority in *Playground* by focusing on what remains after the apparent end of empire rather than conquest, administration, and extraction. The novel's frequent focus on abandoned items floating in the water is the most powerful way to express this theme. Plastic in *Playground* is a colonial material, not only a source of pollution. It bears the mark of global systems that were initially structured by imperial trade routes and subsequently strengthened by consumer capitalism. Once a route for colonial ships carrying goods, labour, and phosphate, the ocean is today a conduit for garbage that follows similar routes. In this way, plastic retraces the paths of empire, but in the other direction: waste moves from the centre back into colonial and postcolonial areas rather than resources moving from the colony to the centre.

A very disturbing scene in Richard Powers *Playground* is when Inna Aroita and her daughter find the corpse of a dead albatross lying on the shore of the island. On further observation, they realize that the belly of the bird does not contain fish or natural remains but pieces of plastic waste bottle tops, wrappers, and other man-made trash swept over the ocean by the consumer culture of today. Distressed, the two carefully remove the plastic from the bird's stomach and bury the body, calling it "death by plastic" (Powers 12). Huggan and Tiffin (2015) argue that "the effects of colonialism on the environment are mostly detrimental, and they can result in the displacement of not only humans, but other living beings as well" (99). It is a powerful ecological metaphor rather than merely an instance of environmental observation.

The albatross is a traditional representation of liberty, endurance, and the force of nature, but it is also a victim of industrial modernity and the global consumer culture. Its decline illustrates how human garbage can infiltrate even the most distant environments. The bird's gut, which served as a feeding area, is transformed into a trash can, emphasizing how unbridled

consumerism and technological advancements transform the conditions of life into those of death. Similar to how foreign administration, economic systems, and cultural standards were imposed on regions by colonial powers, plastic is an unnatural, alien substance that penetrates both the natural world and human activity.

Inna collected, “many trinkets of trash washed up on the island every day” (Powers 130). Like other types of imperial legacies, plastic “trinkets” are not local; rather, they are imported, nonbiodegradable relics of industrialized economies that endure throughout time and space. Plastic functions as Nixon defines *Slow Violence* (2011) “a violence that occurs gradually and out of sight, a violence of delayed destruction that is dispersed across time and space”(2).

Ina Aroita, creates a sculpture from plastic trash on Makatea. The sculpture symbolizes the tension between local traditions and imported cultural narratives, and Makatea’s struggle to reclaim its waste. Aroita, a Pacific Islander, feels uprooted in her colonized islands and the exploitation of her culture by colonization and tourism. Her use of cobalt-blue paint to ruin her sculpture highlights the difficulty of opposing western capitalist logics while creating them. Ina’s sculpture reflects the struggle of displaced people to navigate between memory, myth, and neocolonial modernity, highlighting the impact of America on regional ecosystems and cultures.

Conclusion

Playground is a strong argument on how colonial extraction has transformed into neocolonial governance by use of technology, consumer capitalism and environmental management. The novel illustrates how formal empire still exists in AI systems that purport to know everything about the planet but are still not part of local lives and eco-systems. This physical dominance to an algorithmic control enables exploitation to proceed in the guise of sustainability, efficiency and global good. The process of

environmental destruction in the novel was not happen by accident; it is the immediate consequence of the systems aimed at value extraction and damage externalization to the vulnerable spaces and communities. Plastic waste, specifically, functions as a colonial archive, a material record of imperial trade routes, excessively consuming, and environmental neglecting. Its survival in oceans and islands is a sign of the prolonged postmortem empire, where garbage is the new export instead of raw goods to the ex-colonies. Through his association of AI governance and ecological harm, Powers shows that technological solutions tend to conceal greater inequalities instead of addressing them. Finally, Playground encourages the readers to acknowledge environmental crisis as a historical and political issue, which has its origins in the colonial and neocolonial authorities that are still felt in modern world.

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